

Loan Approval Prediction & Worker's Attendance Performance Analysis

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Abstract - The WeTrack is a mobile application that records and maintains the daily attendance and the wages of the organization that registered into the app. The daily attendance of the list employees is recorded and accordingly the money of each employee is maintained with the base given amount. The attendance as well as the total salary / wages of the workers are calculated and shared with the registered organization manager via mail / mobile number in the format of PDF. The attendance has the facilities of the marking Absent, Full Attendance, as well as Half Attendance accordingly of the worker's arrival at the workplace. The salary is also calculated as per the attendance. The notifications of the corresponding analysis of the maintenance of the record are also mentioned to the manager.

Keywords - Data Mining, Data Analysis, GuassianNB, Decision Tree, Linear Regression (LR)

I. INTRODUCTION

The companies like agriculture based estates, often provides loan / advance to their daily workers for their additional needs. These given advances are then repaid by the workers after some durations and those durations are recorded for the future purposes. But, such privilege of providing the advance fees to the workers can be taken as advantage by the workers who aren't efficient in repaying these debts. So, some analysis of all workers has to be made before paying such advances to them. Using Machine Learning algorithms, we could achieve such analysis and by using these algorithms we could predict with better percent of workers who would consider the regular repay of the advance loans / fees taken. Nowadays, most of the companies with online applications on their side, uses these algorithms to predict the employees' performance instead of manually check the employees' performance. So, using these algorithms we would also check the workers' performance like workers' daily attendance analysis. Using these the companies' managers' and owners' workload will be lifted thus making their life simpler.

Using algorithms & models like GuassianNB, Linear Regression is crucial methodology for prediction purposes and Machine Learning for implementing loan defaulters. By analysing Kaggle or customized datasets, we can use logistic regression models to calculate various performance measures. These algorithms can provide significant insights by incorporating personal attributes of customers, such as workers' total attendances, attendance status, credit score, previous loan taken, total loan repaid, loan repaid duration period, and more. It's essential to consider these factors alongside checking account information when determining the probability of loan default.

Using GuassianNB, Decision Tree approach, we can identify the right customers to provide the advance / loans by accurately evaluating the likelihood of default on a advances. These model suggests that owners should not only approve loans to efficient customers but also take into account other factors that play a crucial role in credit decisions and predicting loan / advance defaulters.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

a) Research Paper 01

Ketki Kinkar, Sharayu Dosalwar, Dr. Nitin Pise and Rahul Sannat [1] first described how clients' actual overhead costs disappeared as a result of the system's capacity to forecast loan approval. They made it clear that while banks can sell a variety of goods through our banking system, credit lines are their main source of income. As a result, they will presumably make money from the interest on the loans they make. The profitability of a bank is impacted by loans or by whether borrowers repay or default on their loans. The bank can lower its stock of non-performing assets by valuing loan defaulters. Since accurate forecasts are essential for maximising profits, it is crucial to compare and contrast the various techniques. A logistic retrogression model is an essential tool in predictive analytics for investigating the problem of forecasting loan defaulters. To conduct research and make predictions, Kaggle data are used. Logistic regression models were used to obtain the dynamic performance metrics.

The model is significantly better because it considers factors other than checking account information, which reveals a client's wealth (specific attributes of guests include scale, dependents, credit score, credit quantum, credit period, and so on), that should be taken into account when properly calculating the probability of loan dereliction. As a result, by assessing the liability of loan dereliction, the right guests to target for loan approval may be dynamically linked utilizing a logistic retrogression approach. The model recommends that a bank should consider a customer's other characteristics, which are important for forming credit judgements and forecasting loan defaulters, in addition to whether or not to accept loans to obese consumers. As the demand for goods and services rises and the amount of capital credit granted, people are more eager than ever to take credit. Computer software has taken the place of the physical interface as more people from all over the world—Urban, Rural, and Semi-Urban—drive for a high demand for credit.

The highest level of delicacy from the logistic retrogression model was attained in their model's prediction

of whether the loan will be approved or denied. The fashionable case delicacy obtained on their dataset is 0.785. Their model was acceptable to determine whether the dataset's aspirants would predict a certain aspirant's loan eligibility by mentioning his row number. Higher income and fewer loan requests from applicants increase the likelihood of approval. For instance, a company's decision to approve or deny a client's loan can be influenced by the client's gender and relationship status. This can assist the banking industry develop more efficient distribution channels. The highest level of delicacy from the logistic regression model was attained in their model's prediction of whether the loan will be approved or denied. The fashionable case delicacy obtained on their dataset is 0.785. Their model was acceptable to determine whether the dataset's aspirants would predict a certain aspirant's loan eligibility by mentioning his row number. Higher income and fewer loan requests from applicants increase the likelihood of approval. For instance, a company's decision to approve or deny a client's loan can be influenced by the client's gender and relationship status. This can assist the banking industry develop more efficient distribution channels.

b) Research Paper 02

The logistic regression analysis, Python datasets, and system were developed by Shahriar H., Tao L, Zhang H Li Z, Qian Y and Bhattacharya P [2] utilized to establish various bracket key values for critical analysis based on the data fraction of unbalanced CSV. They concentrated on the improvement of the Sigmoid function, the gradient descent method for calculating the regression coefficient, the definition of the error function, and the logistic mathematical model.

As a result, the accuracy has practically held steady while the number of repetitions and classification impact have both improved. They clarified that, in plainer terms, a bracket algorithm is a basic cognitive mechanism for classifying or ordering effects or samples. There are two steps involved in using the bracket algorithm in machine literacy. The bracket algorithm's first stage, known as training or fit, makes use of the A.K. markers dataset. Numerous bracket algorithms are available in machine literacy and are comparable to logistic regression, decision trees, SVM, naive bayes, KNN, etc.

Each algorithm has a unique starting point or procedure, as well as advantages and disadvantages and potential applications. Additionally, bracket problems in the real world can have more than two markers, such as brackets for flower species, fruit species, objects, etc. A dataset's distribution may be slightly or significantly unbalanced. Although perfectly equal distribution is incredibly rare, most of the time there is a slight bias in favor of one class.

Similar scripts often have distributions that are heavily skewed, resulting in one nonage class data point for hundreds, thousands, or even millions of maturity class data points. Another method is useful in logistic regression to deal with the imbalance distribution. This is done in order to align the class weights with the class distribution. The class-weights determine how severely the algorithm is penalized for each incorrect class vaticination. The fashionable weights practice in the event of an unstable marker distribution is to employ the antipode of the marker distribution. We can specify weights as the antipode of the marker distribution in our

collection since the marker distribution is 199. Use a weight of 1 for maturity classes and a weight of 99 for non-age classes. Therefore, the punishment for administering the vaccine incorrectly in the nonage class would be 99 times harsher than in the maturity class. Additionally, we would expect our model to perform better than the dereliction one, or former model, with these class-weight values.

c) Research Paper 03

I. R. Smith and A. Riyanto [3] Using the descriptive scheme system, interviews, and document analysis, their research intends to create a system that supports the administration of attendance and the attendance of logging workers effectively and efficiently. So that it may create an RFID-grounded attendance system, which can aid in lubricating the attendance tracking and provide an evaluation of the productivity of the company's employees for the advancement of the organization. a dataset using just necessary variables and parameters. The explanations for the issues and their remedies are given in the clearest and easiest way possible. Understanding the given data flow diagram's architecture and the needs for both my loan approval prediction and the attendance performance analysis was helpful.

In order to collect administration data on hand attendance effectively and efficiently, this project attempts to build an attendance system. To create an efficient and efficient attendance system, the system used descriptive scheme, interview and document analysis connected to hand attendance. The study's findings led to the creation of an attendance system with features for absenteeism as well as the ability to save worker working hours, hand position information, and employment reports for daily and annual employees. This attendance system helps the clerk fill out hand data, as well as gives the vice director daily reports on hand work and aids the vice director in giving the main director an annual report on hand work, making it simpler to evaluate the performance of the company hand for company progress.

d) Research Paper 04

S. Sivagobika, S. Praba, N. Magesh M.E., Dr. P. Thangaraj, and R. Mohana Priya [4] Their primary goal was to use the Decision Tree technique to estimate the performance of hands. They employed data mining techniques that can be used to forecast an employee's success while working for an organization, such as decision trees, rule mining, clustering, etc. The hand facts are approximated for giving creation, monthly proliferation, and career progress in their testament. The decision tree algorithm is used to convert the literal data from the table into a measure of literacy, and the performance is established by comparing a hand's characteristics to the classification rules produced by the decision tree classifier. In this study, information about employees is gathered, a decision tree is made using literal data, evaluated using hand-related features, and then the creation is approved or rejected. Information on a hand is gathered using the stoner interface. This data is compared to the training data stored in the decision tree. The hand will either receive monthly proliferation or creation, which is the final decision to be made.

e) Research Paper 05

Priyanka Bankar, Rutuja Divate, Anushri Papinwar, Aditi Marne [5] describe how SKP styles for software analysis and design were used to produce a data operation system for hand performance targets. Modeling for object visualization with the Unified Modeling Language and a Model View Controller (MVC) system grounded on an open-source frame of origin The expression "SKP Assessment Analysis" refers to an Indonesian government regulation that assesses the position of performance success grounded on quantitative factors, quality aspects, timing, and cost that compare the completion of the task to the destined target. The SKP data operation system has been bettered as a result of this trouble. to ameliorate operation performance in dealing with data vacuity, monitoring conditions, and decision making grounded on performance and material policymakers.

III. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

The system has a critical employee analysis feature which analyze the workers' overall performance, attendance performance, loan-based predictions. These functions are crucial for the customer as company owner, so such system should provide the results of these analysis or prediction with best possible solutions and outputs. Without precise output, the company will be an adverse bad effect which would cause the workers in the company to lose hope and trust towards the company and thus in result reduce the trust towards the system and thereby loose the popularity and usage of the mentioned system.

Thus, the evaluation of the performance of the various factors like finding best suitable algorithms, algorithm analysis, accuracy level, etc is crucial for the system. The organization using this system should be able to predict all kinds of the possibility/results for their employees. The attendance analysis of all kinds of the employees/workers should be reviewed and should be visually visible to the organizations.

After thorough study and analysis, we found that the algorithms like Gaussian Elimination, Linear Regression and Decision Tree should be key focuses for our functionalities. These algorithms are chosen based on the study of the various factors like time complexity, scalability, accuracy, efficiency, etc.

A. Algorithms Used & its Analysis

After careful analysis and requirements for the system, we calculated factors, models, etc and finally make to the conclusion that the best suitable algorithms for the system would be - GaussianNB Classifier & Linear Regression.

a) GaussianNB Classifier:

Gaussian The extension of Naive Bayes is Naive Bayes. This study is concerned with acquiring data about employees, developing a decision tree from the literal data, assessing the decision tree using hand-related qualities, and choosing whether or not to approve the development. To learn more about a hand, utilize the stoner interface. It compares this data to the training data stored in the decision tree. The final decision is whether the hand will receive creation or proliferation each month.

Fig 01 : Gaussian Naïve Bayes Classifier – Data Flow Diagram

A probabilistic machine learning approach called Naive Bayes can be applied to a variety of bracket tasks. Naive Bayes typically performs tasks like bracketing documents, spam screening, vaticination, and more. Thomas Bayes' discoveries served as the foundation for this method, hence its name. The algorithm integrates features into its model that are independent of one another, hence the name "Naive". It is based on a probabilistic model, allowing for easy decipherment of the algorithm and quick, real-time predictions.

When dealing with continuous data, we frequently encounter the fact or circumstance that the classes are distributed normally when this type of data is associated with them. The likelihood of such a feature is assumed to be -

$$P(x_i | y) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma_y^2}} \exp\left(-\frac{(x_i - \mu_y)^2}{2\sigma_y^2}\right)$$

Fig 02 : Likelihood of a feature via GaussianNB

The operation of a Gaussian Naive Bayes (GNB) classifier is shown in the picture below. Every data point's z-score distance from each class mean is calculated; this is the distance from the class mean divided by the class's average deflection. As a result, we can observe that the Gaussian Naive Bayes can be effectively used and has a somewhat distinct path.

Fig 03 : Working of GaussianNB

b) Linear Regression:

In order to predict the outcome of future occurrences, the user of the linear regression method is given a direct relationship between a self-dependent variable and a dependent variable. However, both the independent and dependent variables change over time. The retrogression model predicts the dependent variable, which is the response or outgrowth variable being analyzed or explored. Direct retrogression, then, is a supervised learning technique that forecasts for continuous or numeric variables like deals, payments, age, product pricing, etc. by modeling a close link

between variables. This analytical approach is useful when there are at least two variables included in the data, as is the case with stock request foretelling, portfolio management, scientific analysis, etc.

Fig 04 : Linear Regression's Best Fit Line

In the figure given above,

X-axis= Independent variable,

Y-axis= Affair/ dependent variable,

Line of retrogression= Stylish fit line for a model.

The data points are then combined to create a line that accurately addresses all the problems. As a result, it is known as the "stylish fit line." Finding this chic fit line shown in the below graphic is the goal of the direct retrogression algorithm. Linear regression is a most widely used, efficient algorithm / statistical tool used in data science, because of its features and upper hands such as:

1. Easy implementation
2. Interpretability
3. Scalability
4. Optimal for online settings

The most effective outcome for the solution can be determined by considering the Cost Function, which is a crucial element to consider when choosing an algorithm or model. The Cost Function corrects the regression coefficients and measures, demonstrating how the optimum answer for a linear regression is achieved. The primary purpose of this cost function is to determine the degree of accuracy of the mapping function that is used to map the input and output variables. The cost function used in linear regression is called Mean Squared Error (MSE). It displays the average squared difference between the expected and actual values. Simply said, MSE may be calculated using linear regression as follows:

$$MSE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - (mx_i + b))^2$$

Fig 05: Mean Squared Error Formula for Linear Regression

We will use the MSE function to change the values of a0 and a1 so that the MSE value settles at the minima, keeping in mind that y= Actual Values and yi= Predicted Values. To lower the cost function, alter the model's xi, b (a0, a1) parameters. The grade descent method can be used to estimate these parameters and calculate the cost function value.

B. Accuracy Analysis

After careful analysis of the algorithm, the best 3 algorithm found which is more suitable for the proposed system is Decision Tree, GaussianNB and Linear Regression. These 3 algorithms, when tested with sample data, the success ratio is greater than 92 % which is also given in table format below.

Operation	Sample	Successes	Fail	Success Ratio
GaussianNB	1000	956	44	95.6%
Decision Tree	500	490	10	98%
Linear Regression	2000	1890	110	94.5%

Fig 06. Model Accuracy Table

Here, in the GaussianNB, after evaluating the accuracy and its performance in the system, I can say that Gaussian Algorithm has time complexity of

$$O(n^3)$$

or cubic complexity, whereas Cramer's method has complexity factorial complexity

$$O((n + 1)!)$$

Also, consider the evaluation of the Linear Regression used for the Monthly & Yearly Attendance Analysis, the accuracy is records as 94.5% and its time complexity is cumulatively calculated as

$$O(n^2)$$

C. Overall Analysis

After analyzing all of the factors, the GaussianNB and Linear Regression can be evaluated as a best suitable solution for the problem in the system. The Metrics like time complexity, accuracy, scalability and interpretability, etc suits in the most manner for the solution and use these algorithms helps the system to provide best solution to the customer with optimized result. The analysis after careful study has that –

- The time complexity which is the measure of the amount of the time that the algorithm takes to complete is obtained with adequate output via minimal delay.
- The Accuracy as mentioned before in the figure 06, the accuracy obtained from the model used is more than 92% which is better for the proposed functions implemented.

- The Linear Regression evaluates the accuracy based on the factors like efficiency of the linear function used to fit the input-output pairs.
- Considering the scalability of the used algorithm, the GaussianNB is less scalable than the linear regression but more sustainable and accurate than the other compared algorithm. Since, the linear regression can be implemented using parallel processing techniques, the scalability of this algorithm is higher and also is best suitable for the large datasets, which in turn is beneficial for the proposed system.

Since the proposed system uses dataset of 1,000-10,000 of data, the linear regression can be used to get more accurate results.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

The implementation of the loan approval feature for the workers and the attendance performance analysis of the workers, both are successfully implemented using Machine Learning with the help of the Flask Project. At the implementation at the initially phase, the integration of the python project to the system, i.e., Android Application was quiet a challenge. Initially, the integration of the Machine Learning feature was using “chaquo.python”, a python integration package or dependency implemented to install, run and execute python. The implementation of this methodology was quite a success, but a later stage, as the requirements for the python packages increased, the system got slower and execution time increased due to high size in it. So, we had to backout from the methodology.

Later, with great vast research and visit to various live projects, we got a success implementation of python for Machine Learning. It was using API Request and API Call. In simpler words, the python project for performing the predictions and Machine Learning features is first hosted into a live server which runs 24/7 This gives the Advantage of calling the python functions at any time and from anywhere. In the python functions, the code is also written is such a way that the parameters for the execution like the Test Data are received as a JSON Request and then used for the prediction. Then later at the application phase, the Android Project/System is implemented with the packages and dependencies to call the API Request and perform the python implementation. As told before, in the proposed system, the implementation of the topics is implemented using API call and this API Call and API Requests are added to the Android Project using Dependency called “VolleyAPI”. The dependency code using in the Android Project is :

**“implementation 'com.android.volley:volley:1.2.1'
implementation 'org.apache.poi:poi:3.17”**

The code to connect to the online python server, we use Android Code using Java Language. The screenshots of the code are given below:

```

RequestQueue queue = Volley.newRequestQueue(context);
String url = "https://wetrackpredictions.pythonyanwhere.com/AttendanceAnalysis";

Long val1 = present_count;
Long val2 = half_day_count;
Long val3 = absent_count;

JsonObjectRequest request = new JsonObjectRequest(Request.Method.POST, url, null,
    response -> {
        try {
            String prediction_res = response.getString("attendance_analysis_res");
            String prediction_status = response.getString("attendance_analysis_status");

            float result = Float.parseFloat(prediction_res);
            DecimalFormat df = new DecimalFormat("0.##");
            result = Float.parseFloat(df.format(result));

            float rate_val = result * 5;
            holder.analysis_item_ratingbar.setRating(rate_val);

        } catch (JSONException e) {
            Log.d("volley_error", "Some Error occurred while parsing json data !! Error : " + e.getMessage());
        }
    }, error -> {
        Log.d("volley_error", "Some Error occurred while retrieving json data !! Error : " + error.getMessage());
    });
@Override
public byte[] getBody() {
    }
    }
    
```

Fig 07 : Java Code – VolleyAPI Integration – Screenshot 01

```

@Override
public byte[] getBody() {
    HashMap<String, Object> params = new HashMap<>();
    params.put("val1", val1);
    params.put("val2", val2);
    params.put("val3", val3);
    String requestBody = new JSONObject(params).toString();
    return requestBody.getBytes();
}

@Override
public @Nullable Map<String, String> getHeaders() {
    HashMap<String, String> headers = new HashMap<>();
    headers.put("User-Agent", "Mozilla/5.0");
    return headers;
}

@Override
public String getBodyContentType() { return "application/json"; }
};
queue.add(request);
    
```

Fig 08 : Java Code – VolleyAPI Integration – Screenshot 02

This all was the code and analysis of the integration of the python project to the system i.e., Android Application. Now, let see how the python code and its code works. To make it simpler to get values from the system sources, we first established a Flask project framework in the Python project.

The Flask is utilized due of its many benefits and features, including its simplicity, built-in development debugger and server, integrated support for unit testing, and many other things. The Flask project makes it simple to give the parameters from the user side and its implementation is much less sophisticated than others framework. In this, we have implemented the functionalities via various functions which is mapped using mapping routes. This makes it easier to connect to the functions and pass the test variables to predict.

```

from flask import Flask, jsonify, request
import numpy as np
import LoanPredictionModel as lpm
import AttendanceAnalysisModel as sam

app = Flask(__name__)

# SendLikeGetAttendance
@app.route('/LoanPredict', methods=['GET', 'POST'])
def LoanPredict():
    if request.method == "POST":
        req_data = request.get_json()
        val1 = req_data['val1']
        val2 = req_data['val2']
        val3 = req_data['val3']
        val4 = req_data['val4']
        val5 = req_data['val5']

        model = lpm.load_loan_pickle()
        X_test = np.array([[val1, val2, val3, val4, val5]])
        if model != None:
            y_pred = model.predict(X_test)
            return jsonify({"loan_prediction_res": str(y_pred[0]), "loan_prediction_status": "Success"})
        else:
            return jsonify({"loan_prediction_res": "Error", "loan_prediction_status": "Failure"})
    
```

Fig 09 : Flask Project Screenshot

In this, 1) the GaussianNB is used for the Loan Approval Prediction and 2) The Linear Regression is used for the worker's Attendance Performance Analysis.

Firstly, GaussianNB along with necessary imports used for the Loan Approval Prediction is imported into the Code using packages like :

```
import pandas as pd
from sklearn.naive_bayes import GaussianNB
from os.path import isfile, dirname, join
import pickle
```

Fig 10: Python Code – Package import statements

Then, the GaussianNB is initialized using the GaussianNB function and its from the dataset imported, we separate the import variables and output to different sets. This is done to train the model for the prediction via GaussianNB.

```
gnb = GaussianNB()
gnb.fit(X, y)

X_test= np.array([[val1,val2,val3,val4, val5]])
y_pred = gnb.predict(X_test)
return y_pred[0]
```

Fig 11: Python Code – Model Initialization and Model Training

At initial stage, the model was trained at every stage of the API Request and API Call, but put overhead on the server and thus increased the execution time. So, to change the situation and optimize the API Call, the solution that was found and thus implemented was to create a pickle file that would save the train model in a class format.

The pickle file is used so that the model is trained only once and then used multiple times and thus reduce the execution time. The predicted values show the same accuracy level while testing the data. This is done via implementing the model training into a function and calling that function only once in which the pickle file is also created. Then after that, the pickle file is read instead of the function to predict.

```
def loan_prediction_model():
    cibil_data = pd.read_csv("loan_approval_dataset.csv")
    x = cibil_data.iloc[:, :-1].values
    y = cibil_data.iloc[:, -1].values
    gnb = GaussianNB()
    gnb.fit(X, y)
    with open("loan_pred_pickle_model.pkl", 'wb') as f:
        pickle.dump(gnb, f)
    return pickle.load(open("loan_pred_pickle_model.pkl", "rb"))

def load_loan_pickle():
    model_path = "loan_pred_pickle_model.pkl"
    if isfile(model_path):
        with open(model_path, "rb") as f:
            try:
                return pickle.load(f)
            except Exception:
                return None
    else:
        return loan_prediction_model()
```

Fig 12 : Python Code – Pickle File Generation Code

Fig 13: Python Project Directory – Showing the pickle file created

Finally, the output is sent back as a response to the user who made the request. Any error in the code is caught in the code and any error in the Server Side is handled by the VolleyAPI Code. As the loan approval is a classification methodology, we have modified the output such that the output generated in the format of 0's and 1's.

```
from flask import Flask, jsonify, request
import numpy as np

def loanApprovalPredict(val1, val2, val3, val4):
    model = load_loan_pickle()
    X_test = np.array([[val1, val2, val3, val4]])
    if model != None:
        y_pred = model.predict(X_test)
        return y_pred[0]
    else:
        return -1

print("The Loan Approval Prediction for the sample data is : 1")
```

Fig 14: Loan Approval Prediction Output

Now, coming to the Attendance Performance Analysis using Linear Regression, the Implementation of this features is also same as that of the Loan Approval Prediction. Here also, the packages required to import the Linear Regression along with the other packages to imported and then the Linear Regression Model is initialized and trained.

```
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
from sklearn.linear_model import LinearRegression
```

Fig 15: Python Code – Package import statements

```
lin_reg = LinearRegression()
lin_reg.fit(X,y)

X_test= np.array([[val1, val2, val3]])
y_pred = lin_reg.predict(X_test)
return y_pred[0]
```

Fig 16: Python Code – Model Initialization and Model Training

Fig 17 :Worker’s Attendance Performance Prediction Output

The other way factor is the datasets used in the project for the data prediction. The dataset is created by carefully evaluating the requirements for the project and its parameters. The dataset if not carefully evaluated the risk of predicting the wrong output is high. So, the first main priority is the built a dataset with enough amount of rows/data to predict a highly efficient results.

c1	c2	c3	c4	output
6000	5000	6	4	0
2000	1500	2	1	1
4000	3000	4	3	0
8000	7000	8	6	0
5000	4000	5	3	1
3000	2000	3	2	1
7000	6000	7	5	0
4000	2500	4	3	0
8000	7000	8	6	0
9000	8000	9	7	0

Fig 18:Loan Approval Prediction Dataset

present_fd_count	present_hd_count	absent_count	output
2	1	0	0.83
0	3	2	0.17
1	1	1	0.50
3	0	0	1.00
2	0	1	0.67
1	2	0	0.75
0	1	2	0.08
2	0	1	0.42
1	1	1	0.83
0	2	1	0.33

Fig 19: Worker’s Attendance Performance Dataset

V. CONCLUSION

The proposed theory and this paper have concentrated on the ability of the Loan Prediction Mechanism and also Employee Attendance Performance Analysis. As proposed in the system, the use of various algorithms like GaussianNB, Decision Tree and Linear Regression has been made making the system more accurate to predict and analysis the daily waged workers. By collecting data from various sources like Kaggle, ChatGPT, Google, etc, we have gathered efficient data for the dataset, which results in predicting the customer’ information more accurately and letting the users more comfortable with the system.

The use of GaussianNB for the Loan Approval Prediction mechanism/functionality, the customer i.e., company is given the ability to predict the chances of knowing the good employee/worker who would periodically pay back the advances taken. As the GaussianNB algorithm provides the output in the format of bits i.e., 0’s OR 1’s, it is more comfortable to predict the loan approval. And the accurate of

the GuassianNB algorithm/model is 0.91 to 0.96, the model is best suitable for such a situation where the time is crucial.

Also, we use Linear Regression for the Employee Attendance Prediction, to show an average/attendance based analyzed graph or charts to know the performance and the consistency of the employee presence in the field. The proposed system i.e., The app shows a Pie Chart as well as a 5-star rating about the workers’ attendance, which let the company owner visualize the workers’ presence on the field which out visiting the field itself. This reduces the overhead of the customer/company owner. While there are challenges in implementing such a system, including the need for reliable sensor data and appropriate training data for the machine learning algorithms, the benefits of improved safety and reduced accident rates make it a promising avenue for further research and development.

A. Result Analysis

The result of the implementation of these proposed models and algorithm in the system has successfully been implemented with high success rate. The loan approval prediction using GaussianNB and Monthly Attendance Analysis of the workers have been successfully performed. As mentioned in the “Implementation” topic, the python-based Flask Project using these algorithms is hosted/executed in an online platform to run 24/7. And after that, the python flask code is called using API using various available libraries.

a) Loan Approval Prediction:

As the system calls the python code using API Call, the output is return back after predicting the test data in form of response. For the trail purpose, we called the python function hosted onto the server using sample test data using an application called “POSTMAN”. The postman helps the developers to make sample debug/testing and real time API calls, and shows the result of the API call made.

Below given image is the example of such call for the demonstration of the running Machine Learning Prediction Code which is hosted. As the Loan Approval Prediction gives only two possible answers/output, i.e., ‘0’ indicating that the loan approval algorithm rejects that person’s “Advance Request for more Money” and ‘1’ indicating that the loan approval algorithm approves that person’s “Advance Request for more Money”. Examples of both of the conditions are mentioned below for references.

Fig 20 – Loan Approval Prediction’s Output 01

Fig 21 – Loan Approval Prediction’s Output 02

Fig 23 – Attendance Analysis – Output 02

b) **Employee Attendance Analysis:**

Similar to the Loan Approval Prediction Feature, the Employee Attendance Analysis is also recorded and tested with sample test data for demonstration purposes. Here also the use of the POSTMAN is made to test the API call and the result. Here in the Attendance Analysis, instead of only bits values like 0 and 1, we would need more than that like mid values to determine the attendance analysis and the worker’s efficiency on coming to the working field. So, instead in here we also get values in between 1 and 0 like decimals values. Achieving that, we can determine the analysis of the attendance of the workers. Now, the case is that it is difficult to use GuassianNB algorithm to determine the output here.

It is because the GuassianNB is the more efficient in classification model-based values instead of the continuous values. It supports the continuous set of values as output but more efficient for classification-based. Here comes the use of Linear Regression, which is efficient, scalable and supervised learning-based algorithm with is more suitable for continuous values of outputs. Please refer the below figures to understand the output of the analysis.

Fig 22 – Attendance Analysis – Output 01

B. **Future Enhancement**

Currently the proposed idea and its implementation is performed free of cost and with little weight algorithms. The usage of the GuassianNB and Linear Regression is much simpler. But in turn is slower than some algorithms. There are still some algorithms which is more accurate result providing and efficient than the current used algorithms. But considering the current state of the project and its limitations, we have considered to use/implement those higher efficient algorithms more future update.

In the future basis, the proposed system would be added with more efficient algorithms like RandomForestClassifier, Modified Decision Tree (Modifies ID3), etc into the proposed system to enhance the system’s accuracy performance. Also, we consider to add more Machine Learning Modules to our system to analyze the workers and give accuracy knowledge about the field.

a.

b. **VI. .REFERENCE**

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